

Phase Studies in the System $\text{Fe}_x\text{Zn}_{1-x}\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_6$

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Received August 1, 1970

Though the structure of Columbite has been studied by many workers¹⁻³ the present system is not studied. It is expected that in Columbite lattice when Zinc is substituted for Iron, a series of solid solutions should result. To confirm this the present system is studied.

The samples are prepared by mixing the component oxides in appropriate proportions and firing them at 1000° for 15 hrs. and at 1350° for 3 hrs. The samples thus obtained were finely ground and passed through 300 mesh. The Philips X-ray diffractometer with Mo K_α radiation filtered through Zirconium foil was used. The diffractometer was operated at 30 kilovolts and 15 milliamps and was driven at the rate of 1° per minute. The charts thus obtained were used for the calculation of the lattice constants and to observe the phases developed. The results are shown in table 1.

TABLE 1

Sample No.	Composition	Molecular Weight	Colour	Phases Present
Z ₁	$\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{Zn}_{0.2}\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_6$	339.60	grey	Columbite : a = 4.918, b = 14.11, c = 5.748 Å
Z ₂	$\text{Fe}_{0.6}\text{Zn}_{0.4}\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_6$	341.46	light grey	Columbite : a = 4.922, b = 14.11, c = 5.748 Å
Z ₃	$\text{Fe}_{0.4}\text{Zn}_{0.6}\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_6$	343.87	deep brown	Columbite : a = 4.949, b = 14.11, c = 5.748 Å
Z ₄	$\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_6$	345.27	light brown	Columbite : a = 4.962, b = 14.11, c = 5.748 Å
Z ₅	ZnNb_2O_6	347.18	light pink	Columbite : a = 4.968, b = 14.11, c = 5.748 Å

It is observed that on substituting Zn^{2+} (0.83 Å) for Fe^{2+} (0.74 Å) in the Columbite lattice, the lattice dimensions were constant along b_0 and c_0 axes, but increased along a_0 axis. Throughout only one phase of Columbite was observed.

On examining the Columbite structure it is observed that Mo_6 octahedra are linked together in the form of chains ranged along a_0 axis and held together by sharing edges. On introduction of bigger ion Zn^{2+} the arrangement remains the same but the expansion of lattice takes place along a_0 axis which is in accordance with the present studies.

REFERENCES

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